

Nutritional Status among Marginalised Groups- A Critical Review of Health Outcomes through SES and NFHS, India

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Abstract

The nutritional condition of children serves as a vital indicator for evaluating overall health outcomes. Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 3 – ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all – this area demands focused attention. One of its key aims is to prevent diseases and safeguard children’s lives. In this regard, discussions on nutrition and health outcomes hold great significance. National-level surveys, such as the National Family Health Survey (NFHS), provide valuable data to assess children’s nutritional status. It is essential to analyze the health and nutrition of marginalized groups, as evidence indicates notable differences among various social categories. Although the health of all children requires consideration, understanding disparities based on socioeconomic and regional backgrounds is crucial for effective policymaking and program design. Despite several government health initiatives, marginalized populations continue to experience poorer health conditions due to socioeconomic disadvantages. Hence, this paper critically examines the nutritional and health status of children from marginalized communities to explore how socioeconomic factors influence their health outcomes.

Key words: Sustainable Development Goals, Nutritional Status And Health Outcome, Marginalised Group, Social Economic Status.

Introduction

Inadequate nutrition intake affects the health of the population at large and is a severe public health issue that is acknowledged worldwide. Shockingly, the data discovered that worldwide 2.3 billion adults, around 30% of the global population, are suffering from some or other form of malnutrition. This alarming figure highlights the immediate need for action to address this issue and to raise dialogue about public health policy. Additionally, a progress report by the UN revealed that one in every ten people is suffering from hunger-related problems around the globe, and as far as regular lack of food access is concerned, one in three people is lagging behind it (Feeding India, 2022). Further, the same report revealed that India's contribution to the global malnutrition crisis is significant; according to data, 14.7% of its population is unable to receive adequate nutrition. Notably, such a situation is terrible for children because data suggests that one-third of undernourished children worldwide are Indian, which is a matter of serious concern. Geographically within the Indian territory, the states of Maharashtra, Gujarat and Bihar have the worst levels of malnutrition (Feeding India, 2022). A joint report by FAO, WHO, UNICEF, WFP and IFAD revealed that 42.1% of people cannot afford healthy food globally, and out of that, 74.1% of the population is Indian, which means that more than one hundred crore people are bound to eat food with inadequate nutrition in India (Sharma, 2023). Further, the latest report by the United Nations Food and Agricultural Organisation discovered that 85% of the population (approx. 314 million people) of South Asia are undernourished (Hussain, 2023).

In India, there are certain communities that are exposed to multiple forms of discrimination and marginalisation due to various social, political, and economic reasons. According to the Office of the Registrar General and Census Commission (2011) data, in India, there are two major marginalised communities: scheduled castes, which constitute 16.6% of the total population and scheduled tribes, 8.6% of the total population (Bhagat, 2024). The other data set revealed that in India, SC, ST and Muslims are 450 million, which makes them the largest marginalised social group globally; consequently, they are forced to face violence, discrimination, exclusion and marginalisation (Priya & Paikra, 2022). The same report claims that due to socio-economic factors and limited access to health care, the health outcomes of these groups are poor and are facing nutritional deficiencies. As a result, the issues of malnutrition and undernutrition are more prevalent among these groups than the general population (Priya & Paikra, 2022).

In 2023, RBI governor Raghuram Rajan stated that to become a developed country, India needs to address the issue of malnutrition (PTI, 2023). It is proven that one's nutritional status has a significant impact on one's health status, and it also holds considerable potential for positive change in one's well-being and health status, as well as for the development of society and nation. Moreover, people's growth, development, infection resistance, body weight, and clinical outcomes are all of these aspects that are significantly impacted by their nutritional intake or status. Hence, for the optimal function of the body, several nutrient groups, including water, minerals, carbohydrates, lipids, proteins, and vitamins, are crucial. Maintaining a nutritious lifestyle and healthy weight can reduce the risk of disease. Cholesterol and high blood pressure, and enhancing energy levels, well-being, and the ability to fight illness, good nutrition can pave the way for a healthier future (Tufts Health Plan Medicare Preferred, nd). Furthermore, it is a robust preventive measure against many diseases, supports better physical and cognitive function, and improves the immune system (CDC, nd). However, the ground scenario is not positive; according to the Centre for Disease and Prevention report (2023), four in ten children and less than one in seven adults eat enough fruits, and less than one in ten children and adults eat the recommended quantity of vegetables daily.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 3, emphasize ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all age groups. This goal specifically focuses on disease prevention and safeguarding children's health. In this regard, understanding the relationship between nutrition and health outcomes becomes essential. The present study examines the nutritional status of marginalized and minority populations in India, with a particular emphasis on women and child health. It further explores the factors contributing to poor health outcomes and the persistent challenges in achieving overall well-being among these groups. Although the Government of India has introduced numerous programs to address malnutrition, marginalized communities continue to experience inferior health conditions due to socioeconomic disparities.

Using data from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS), the study assesses the nutritional and health status of children across various social groups. Reviewing these differences based on socioeconomic and regional backgrounds is crucial for effective policy formulation and ground-level interventions. Hence, this paper critically evaluates the nutritional conditions and health outcomes of marginalized children to better understand the influence of socioeconomic status on their overall health.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research methodology in which information has been mainly gathered from primary as well as secondary sources. Primary Data has been collected from Dhemra Village of Saharsa, Bihar. Dhemra village is selected because this village is the home of mainly Mushhar community. Mushhar community people are the most backward, deprived and poorest among all schedule caste (NHRC, 2018). Three cases were captured in the field. Moreover, since the authors are social workers, hence their other field work experiences related to this study have been also included in the study. Further, through secondary sources such as National Family Health Survey Report (NFHS) - 5, NFHS-4, and NFHS-3, their present health status has been compared to past, and also to capture the reality of their health and nutritional status over a period of time. This helped the researcher

to analyse the health status and nutritional intake of marginalised and minority communities. The supplementary data from the literature and the NFHS survey have been incorporated to fulfil the study's objectives. International and national reports, studies, and news reports have been reviewed to justify the researcher's arguments and highlight people's past and present health status in the marginalised social category. Apart from the data, the author's professional work has also been incorporated into this study. The critical assessment of observations and field intervention have been added to this study.

Literature Review

Marginalised social groups have been facing discrimination and inequality in almost every aspect of their lives for years. Even though legal discrimination against them is prohibited, still the marginalised communities in India are struggling to sustain decent lives in many ways. Even within the marginalised community, the women are more vulnerable and face challenges due to different types of discrimination, as stated by UNICEF that 'she is a woman, she is a Dalit, and she is a Dalit woman' (Humanitarian Aid Relief Trust, UK. 2023) it means they are facing multiple forms of marginalisation. As a result, marginalised communities, in comparison to the dominant community, tend to maintain low health status, and this is primarily due to the challenges they face in access to public resources, services and healthcare.

SC and ST groups in comparison to other social groups having low health status (Puri & Anand, 2015). Further, despite the existing state-sponsored nutrition and welfare intervention schemes, such disparity exists. It indicates that there might be several other social and ecological reasons due to which these, marginalised groups are not getting benefit of these schemes. Further, it is equally important to highlight that among all the religious groups, the health status of women and children belonging to the Muslim community is also low. Merely presence of scheme is not sufficient for maintainance of equality in health status. As far as SC and ST social category is concerned, they also face discrimination in the utilisation of government health services, as a study conducted in five states of 550 villages revealed that 50% of SC and ST children are facing discrimination in the utilisation of the mid day meal scheme (Puri & Anand, 2015). Moreover, regional disparities in terms of healthcare access and outcomes are a significant issue. Several studies have pointed out that there are substantial differences in healthcare services, infrastructure, and health indicators across different regions and states in the country (Mukhopadhyay & West Bengal State University, 2015; Kumari & Raman, 2021; B, S. 2023).

The study on healthcare disparities in Uttar Pradesh found that districts in the western region were more developed in healthcare availability, amenities, and affordability than the eastern districts (Kumari & Raman, 2021). These regional disparities are often rooted in socioeconomic factors, with rural and economically disadvantaged areas facing greater challenges in accessing quality healthcare (B, S. 2023). Factors such as income, education, and social determinants play a key role in shaping these regional differences in health outcomes (Ghosh, 2011; Mukhopadhyay & West Bengal State University. 2015). In terms of health and illness, marginalised communities struggle more and face a disproportionate disadvantage as socio-economic factors play a crucial role, and also minority groups often have access to limited healthcare services and experience lower income and higher poverty rates. Further, in terms of child health and nutrition, a high disparity as well as inequality has been observed among caste groups and a high burden on SC and ST groups. Caste-based inequality is deeply rooted within Indian society and is a reality in India, consequently impacting the health of people (Raushan, Acharya, & Raushan, 2022). The above discussion revealed that marginalised and minority groups face a higher rate of health disparity at national as well as international levels.

Socio-economic status and the health status of the children

Children's health is entirely dependent or affected by family status and social position of the family. As highlighted in Table 3, IMR is highest among children belonging to the SC (32.2) group; anaemia is highest among ST children (72.4). Moreover, 7.6% of SC children and 7.6% of ST children suffered from diarrhoea. These groups are targeted groups and are given special attention at all levels. As a result,

vaccination and immunisation rates have significantly increased among them. However, the vaccination and immunisation percentages are lowest among children belonging to other groups.

Table 3- The health status of children based on social status.

Background	Percentage of children under age 6 years who received immunisation	Percentage of children with diarrhoea	Prevalence of any anaemia in children	Percentage of children age 12-23 months fully vaccinated	Infant mortality rate
Religion					
Hindu	55.4	7.3	67.5	77.4	36.0
Muslim	45.6	7.5	66.8	71.1	27.8
Christian	42.4	6.3	53.1	78.0	12.6
Sikh	40.8	4.8	70.3	79.9	19.6
Caste/tribe					
OBC	59.8	7.1	65.2	77.0	25.5
SC	55.5	7.6	69.5	76.7	32.2
ST	59.1	7.6	72.4	76.5	32.1
Other	45.0	7.2	65.8	75.6	28.0

Source: NFHS 5. (2021). GOI. [2019-21 India National Family Health Survey \[FR375\] \(dhsprogram.com\)](https://dhsprogram.com)

Health and nutritional status of marginalised community

A society works at its optimum level when all people are equally advancing and utilising the resources properly. The social status of people is the major deciding factor for the accessibility and utilisation of services. Most often, social status has a negative impact on unprivileged groups and compels them to be on the margin. The health outcome differences according to social status were assessed using the NFHS data set. The anaemia rate among marginalised communities over a period of 15 years is tracked. In that case, it is clearly visible that more than 50% of them are anaemic, which means that despite several governmental initiatives, their condition has not improved up to a satisfactory level. The NFHS-3 report showed the condition of children belonging to different marginalised communities, and according to the report, 76.8% of ST children, 72.2% of SC children and 70.3% of OBC children were anaemic in India during 2005-2006. To decrease this percentage, special attention was given by the government, and consequently, over ten years during 2015-16, children's condition was comparatively better; the anaemic proportion was slightly decreased among this group, as per the report, 63.3% of ST children, 60.6% of SC children and 58.6% of OBC children were anaemic (NFHS-4). The decline in anaemia rate among children in NFHS-4 from NFHS-3 can be clearly seen over the period of ten years. Nevertheless, their condition deteriorated over the next five years instead of improving. As NFHS-5 shows that 72.4% of ST children, 69.5% of SC children and 65.2% of OBC children are anaemic in India, which should be a significant concern. As the data sets of the past 20 years assessed, it shows that the children belonging to marginalised communities such as SC, ST, and OBC are at the bottom level in terms of health parameters and have a low health status.

Furthermore, during a field study, the researcher observed in the study area that there was a bowl of rice mixed with a small amount of salt; five kids were fighting and snatching among each other to eat that. Such a scenario shows that they are unable to fulfil their basic needs, and even they are unable to have at least two times of proper meals in a day. In such a situation, having a proper nutrient diet is like a dream for them, and that is why most of them are malnourished. However, the right to food, which is a fundamental human right, ensures the accessibility, affordability, adequacy and availability of food to each individual in every circumstance. Hence, being unable to meet an essential nutrient diet is a violation of their fundamental human right. Moreover, article 21 of the Indian constitution guarantees the right to life with dignity to the individual, and this right is primarily dependent on food. A person can never enjoy his/her right to life with dignity if s/he is unable to have nutritious food (NHRC, nd). Further, with the help of the NFHS data set, the health status of men and women

belonging to the marginalised community could be understood. The data gathered on the status of anaemia, nutrition and food consumption. Fruit, milk and curd consumption is crucial for health, and therefore, data analysed on this consumption. Fruit provides several essential nutrients for the body's growth. Fruits, vegetables, milk and curds are essential for maintaining health and are associated with reducing chronic diseases and managing an individual's health. However, the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization and the World Health Organization suggested that everyone consume at least five types of vegetables and fruits daily, which shows the significance of fruits and vegetables in maintaining nutrients (Pem & Jeewon, 2015). Unfortunately, many marginalised people, especially the people of the selected area are not getting adequate meal even for two times in a day.

Table: 4 The pattern of anaemia, nutritional level and food consumption of marginalised groups through NFHS 2005-2021.

S. No	Indicator	NFHS-5 (2019-2021)				NFHS-4 (2015-16)				NFHS-3 (2005-6)			
		SC	ST	OBC	Other	SC	ST	OBC	Oth.	SC	ST	OBC	Other
1.	Anaemia status of children by haemoglobin level	69.5	72.4	65.2	65.8	60.6	63.3	58.6	54.2	72.2	76.8	70.3	63.8
3.	The nutritional status of women (Mean BMI)	22.1	21.1	22.5	23.2	21.4	20.5	21.9	22.7	19.9	19.1	20.4	21.3
4.	Prevalence of anaemia in women	59.2	64.6	54.6	56.4	55.9	59.9	52.2	49.8	58.3	68.5	54.4	51.3
5.	Prevalence of anaemia in men	26.1	32.7	22.6	25.5	23.6	32.0	22.0	20.3	26.6	39.6	22.3	20.9
6.	Women's consumption of fruit	44.4	37.4	50.3	57.9	39.3	32.2	44.9	56.6	32.0	27.4	39.0	48.4
7.	Women's consumption of curd or milk	68.7	54.9	76.5	74.9	62.9	50.1	71.2	72.9	45.3	33.5	60.6	60.4
8.	Men's consumption of fruit	51.6	46.5	56.9	61.2	46.3	36.5	50.5	58.1	39.3	30.5	49.3	54.0
9.	Men's consumption of curd or milk	76.3	66.7	84.2	80.2	71.1	55.8	78.3	78.6	60.0	41.8	73.6	70.1

Source: NFHS 5,4,3(2021, 2016 & 2006) GOI, [NFHS \(rchiips.org\)](https://rchiips.org)

As far as food consumption among the marginalised groups is concerned, it is also deficient among them. They are consuming less fruit, curd, or milk as mentioned above. Moreover, within the group, women are consuming significantly less of these items than men; hence, even in terms of food consumption, there is also significant gender inequality. However, comparing the data from the last 15 years, it can be seen that their food consumption is slightly improving. Even if we look at recent data on women's fruit consumption, we can easily find that only less than 50% of women consume fruit. The recent NFHS-5 data says that only 44.4% of women in the SC community, 37.4% in the ST community, and 50.3% of the OBC community consume fruit. As far as the consumption of curd or milk is concerned, data reveals that 68.7% of women in the SC community, 54.9% of women in the ST community and 76.5% of women in the OBC community are consuming it. According to this data, OBC women consume comparatively more fruit, milk, and curd than SC and ST. Moreover, the consumption rate is lowest among ST groups from NFHS 3 to NFHS 5. Similarly, research also found in the field that the consumption of fruit, milk and curd is very low among children and women belong to marginalised groups.

Further, data related to male consumption of fruit, milk, or curd shows that 51.6% of SC males, 46.5% of ST males, and 56.9% of OBC males consume fruit, whereas the consumption of milk or curd is concerned among these groups; data reveals that 76.3% of SC males, 66.7% of ST males, and 84.2% of

OBC males consume milk or curd. Here, it is important to note that among all the marginalised groups, the consumption of a healthy diet, including fruit, milk or curd, is lowest among ST groups. Several studies have also proven that milk consumption is a healthy diet. It is crucial for maintaining energy levels and is beneficial for hypertension, CRC, obesity, stroke, CVD, metabolic syndrome, osteoporosis, AD, and T2DM (Zhang, 2021). Despite this fact, a significant proportion of the Indian population is deprived of good resources. Several other social factors also consequently force them to live an unhealthy life and healthy diet due to social inequality and unavailability.

Through various health indicators, let us analyse the health status of different social groups and gaps. The NFHS- 3(2005-6) data indicated that 68.5% of women and 39.6% of men from the ST community, 58.2% of women and 23.6% of men in the SC community and 54.4% of women and 22.3% of men in the OBC community were anaemic during 2005-06. Whereas after approx. 15 years at the time of NFHS 5 (2019-21), data indicates that 64.6% of women and 32.7% of men in the ST community, 59.2% of women and 26.1% of men are anaemic in the SC community, and 54.6% of women and 22.6% of the OBC community are anaemic in India. This data highlighted the poor health conditions and also no significant improvement in their health condition in the last 15 years. Even within these groups, the health status of women and children is low in comparison to men, and gender disparity exists between men and women in terms of their health status. Hence, such data shows that women and children are facing multiple forms of marginalisation within society and struggling to fulfil the minimum basic needs.

Struggling life of Mushahars

Case 1

Sakti, who belongs to the Mushahar community. She is a approx. 40-year-old widow women who agreed to participate in the study. She has seven children and nine grandchildren. She is living with all her children and grandchildren along with her mother. She reported no one in her family is employed and she is just managing the basic needs of every family member. When she was asked how she is managing. She replied '*mushar sab jena jibe chhe ona jibe chhiye, kunu puwa pkman ke aas rhe ye, jaih milal bhagwan bharse jibe le saih khake rahlu.* (Like Mushahar people are surviving, similarly we are surviving and managing. We have no desire off sweets or other dishes, whatever god is offering us, that is usually sufficient for us). Researcher with more curiosity, expressed her desire to know more about their day's meal. In response to this question, she said that *-rait me malik ke eha bhoj rhe, dherik ras khana bhinsare khuna dalke rhe ae waha bha gele, aab rait me timon bhat ya sohari je kre putoh beti aar kre jete* (there was a party yesterday night at her landowner house(malik); this morning all the leftovers food from last night's party were given to her. That day she along with all her family members had consumed that food. In dinner her daughter or daughter-in-law will cook rice and vegetables or bread). Further she said that *bhate timon ka lelak te bal bachcha aar ke nik bhel bhore, ekra aar ke bhore uthte khae le dau dau kre lagal, besi khun rait ke bhuklthe sut gel, te kichho te jalkhe debe, jo timon nae rahal te chuche bhato nun khae le jae chhe. Tahi lake raite me bachcha delu.* (She said usually, rice and vegetable are cooked in the night, so that some food could be saved for the children's breakfast of the next day. Children demand breakfast early morning, because many times they sleep early with an empty stomach. Even if there is no vegetable left, they still have rice and salt). When she was asked about her breakfast and other family members breakfast, she said- *hme sab thore bhore bhor khae chhiye. Din me ke ber khaelu, munsa sabhak ke khela ke bad* (Except children, no one eats breakfast. Adult members consume only one time meal in a day; when men finished their meal, after that women eat). Further she said that *- kte se hme sab 4 ber khebe, 1-2 ber me te fatet rahe ye, ohiyo me besi khuna make ke ghaet par rhe chhi.* (How could we eat four times of meal, somehow, we try to manage our one or two times of meals a day. even many times we consume ghaet, a dish made with only corn flour and salt). The everyday experience of shakti reflects her challenging situation in which many people like her are forced to live. In such situation, where they are struggling for two times of meal in that situation nutrition does not exists for them or getting nutritious meal must be extremely challenging for them. Lack of nutrition causes poor health and many diseases.

Case 2

Gajo a 53 old man. His family consists of fourteen members and he reported that only ten to twelve kilograms grains he was getting through PDS which is insufficient for his family and is only for 8 to 10 days of a month. Further, he said that to survive sometimes they have to steal from others field and sometimes they to beg (10-12 kilo ke lagbhag me anaj dae chhe sarkar jae se 8-10 kahuna katlu, okar bad loehr noeckhe – maing chaing ke kahuna jilo). His statement reflects his pathetic condition in which he is surviving.

Case 3

Milk, curd, fruit, juice- we don't get to eat these even in our dreams. Somehow, we manage our everyday rice-roti said by a 20-year-old pregnant female. During the interview, two of her children were sitting in front of us and were eating rice puffs picked from the mud floor. She discussed that she rarely buys pulse or vegetables. Many times, we pick greens, eating leaves and vegetables from somewhere and make the gravy from the same and eat it with rice. Sometimes by catching fish, doka/snail, rat, ghongha and kakhur from nearby ponds we eat nonveg.

None of the women, to whom researcher interacted in the field has mentioned about consumption of nutritious food or food items such as curd, milk, fruit, pulse, salad etc. However, in very minimum income or no income, they can't even afford the same. As all of them mentioned that they are not getting adequate food, in that situation how could they even think about nutritious meal.

Discussion and conclusion

It is the right of every individual to live a healthy life, and it is crucial for them to maintain a healthy and nutritious diet. Social inequality systematically creates discriminatory structures, and due to this structural inequality, the people, especially marginalised sections, are unable to fulfil their basic needs. Consequently, they face several health issues, and their health becomes the biggest concern for themselves, and it is a significant loss for the nation. Systematic discrimination and social exclusion significantly influence individuals' lives, restricting their growth, freedom, and overall well-being. Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 3—ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all—the focus must include disease prevention and child health protection. In this context, analyzing the nutritional status and health outcomes of marginalized children becomes vital. This paper examines the patterns and implications of marginalization in relation to child health outcomes, using data from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS). Findings reveal notable disparities among different social groups. The study highlights the need for targeted policies and exclusive health programs addressing marginalized populations. Social welfare schemes should emphasize measurable outcomes, supported by awareness and sensitization initiatives. Prioritizing the health of women and children, maintaining international quality standards, increasing budget allocations, and fostering partnerships with private stakeholders are essential steps toward achieving equitable and sustainable health outcomes. Health is a fundamental right for everyone, and it should be treated as a fundamental right for everyone, and it should be treated as a fundamental right for everyone, and it should be treated as an inalienable feature of all social policies.

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